

Witness Intimidation and Other Issues Related to Witnesses in Criminal Justice System of Pakistan

Abdul Majid Baloch^{1*}

¹University Law College, University of Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan.

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Author info:

Corresponding Author.
Abdul Majid Baloch.
abdulhasani2007@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Witnesses are important stake holders in criminal justice system because they assist the court in reaching a just conclusion of a case. The situation of witnesses and their welfare, however, is not satisfactory in Pakistan. There are growing cases of witness intimidation in recent history of Pakistan where witnesses of high-profile cases were subject to intimidation. Witnesses of Benazir Bhutto murder case, Wali Khan Babar murder case, Sabeen Mahmood case, Naqebullah Mehsud case was either killed, or threatened due to which the courts were failed to convict the accused. Witness intimidation refers to the practice of causing actual physical harm, extending threats, damaging property etc. Due to this situation witnesses show lack of interest in investigation and judicial process. Apart from intimidation witnesses face several other issues such as bearing expenses of travelling to court, lack of facilities in court premises, unnecessary adjournments, unlimited cross-examination, unfit memory, psychological pressure of confrontation with accused etc. All these issues directly or indirectly effect the trial and resultantly the judiciary fails to meet the ends of justice. This situation can be made better if state authorities realize the sensitivity of the situation and if they are willing to act upon all or any of the suggestions and recommendations given in the article.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The Pakistan is one of the countries with low conviction rates in criminal trials for which the main reasons is considered to be the feelings of insecurity of witnesses. Situation becomes worse when it comes to high profile cases involving influential parties. When witnesses of a particular case fears from giving testimony in a free and fair environment, then it is said that the witness is subjected to witness intimidation. Due to fear and insecurity witnesses show reluctance in cooperating with investigation agencies. Police in Pakistan lacks the basic necessary training to carry out investigation on the parameters of modern era. They only rely on collection of ocular evidence rather than circumstantial or forensic evidence. As a result of this over reliance witnesses often retract from their previous statements when face any threat or insecurity. There are various incidents of witness intimidation and violence in recent history of Pakistan where witnesses of many high-profile cases were harassed, threatened and even killed in the process of investigation and trial which created an environment of fear among civilians and important eyewitnesses. The famous human rights activist Sabeen Mahmood Case is an example where only witness of the case who was her gunman/driver was shot dead in Karachi in 2015 (BBC, 2015). Similarly, in 2020 two important witnesses of Naqeebullah Mehsud's case resiled from their statements (Sahoutara,2020). In same manner Benazir Bhutto assassination case and journalist Wali Khan Babar murder case could not reached a just conclusion due to witness intimidation incidents. Our criminal justice system faces a wide range of problems, as agreed by various experts, one of its main weaknesses is the failure in protection of witnesses.

1. Background of Study

This article aims to look the status of witness intimidation situation in Pakistan by keeping in view various news reports, articles, analysis and findings of various scholars and researchers and bring out a clear picture of witness issues in criminal justice system of Pakistan.

Criminal justice system in Pakistan is facing serious issues and in a recent report published by World Justice Project, in 2023, it is showed that Pakistan ranks 130 among 142 countries in rule of law index (World Justice Project, 2023). This degrading ranking is an alarm for Pakistan's international image and one of its main reasons is critical situation of witness intimidation and other serious issues of witnesses.

There are many occasions where citizens are witnesses of a crime but they show reluctance to come forward in cooperation with police and the main reason for that, may be the feelings of threat of retaliation from offenders. Witness intimidation may be of any form such as, actual threats, threatening phone calls, violence, damage of property, threat or assault to family members of the witness. Such intimidation may be one incident or it may be a series of acts which continues for a longer period until their demands are met. It also happens that the offender commits witness intimidation himself, or when he himself is jail custody through his partners/associates, but the quest for retaliation continues. Witness intimidation may occur in a specific case where it targets individuals to refrain from cooperation with investigation and testimony in courts or it targets entire community members of a locality by spreading a sense of fear for the purpose of not cooperation with police and judicial process. Such actions have serious implications on criminal justice system resulting in low conviction rates (Dedel, 2016)

2. Literature Review

In an online blog writer Pankhuri Anand (2019) asserts that in famous case Indian Supreme Court has examined the role of witnesses in criminal justice system. The court observed that in the dispensation of justice witnesses play an integral role, therefore, legislature should take measures for the protection of witnesses in order to conduct a fair trial (Anand, 2016).

In a famous case in India, Indian Supreme Court observed that witnesses are eyes and ears of justice and their role is very important for quality trial process. The court observed that if the witnesses incapacitated from giving testimony, then the trial is adversely affected. The incapacitation may be due to several reasons like witnesses unable to speak the truth, his negligence, ignorance or some corrupt collusion (Dayal Singh v. State of Haryana, 1998).

The cooperation between victims and witnesses is necessary for judicial process and criminal justice system. In most of the cases witnesses fear to depose in the court of law due to actual threat, harassment or intimidation. The situation gets worse in heinous offences where the accused is an influential party. There are several examples where witnesses of famous cases were killed in Pakistan. Even a witness was targeted in the premises of the court in an incident. Such incidents make it dire need that a witness protection system be implemented. (Bashir, 2019).

Witnesses has the power to decide the whole fate of the case. It is a great challenge to ensure safety of a witness in the administration of justice. It appears in most of the cases that witness

of the case is the victim himself. Protection of the witness becomes necessary duty when the witness is a child, woman or old person. (Prakash & Tiwari 2020).

It is the prime duty of the courts to administer justice and bring the culprits into justice for the wrongs they have committed. Courts can reach a just conclusion through evidences produced by the parties in oral or documentary form. The version of witnesses given in oral form is considered best form of evidence. They play a significant role in criminal justice system. It is however unfortunate, that situation of witnesses turning worse with the passage of every day. There are reports of threat, inducement, harassment, and criminal intimidation of witnesses in various regions. Due to the prevailing environment of fear, witnesses hesitate to assist the court of law or they turn hostile. This issue can be resolved through an effective witness protection scheme. (Rahangdale 2019).

3. Witness Intimidation

Witness tampering is an attempt to prevent, restrict, influence and alter a witness from giving testimony within a judicial proceeding (Wikipedia)

Witness or victim intimidation is the act of threatening, harming, spreading fear towards a witness of a crime in an attempt to prevent him from giving statement to investigation agency or court (Chen, 2009)

Witness tampering is the act of using threats, harassment and influence with the aim of influencing the witness's testimony or preventing the witness from providing evidence in an official proceeding (Merriam-Webster, n.d.)

It is essential element of rule of law that a witness must be able to cooperate with investigation authorities and give evidence in a court of law without fear, intimidation or pressure. Witnesses face a lot of issues among them insecurity, safety and protection are on top. They face harassment and threats from the accused, influential parties and organizations to deter them from deposing against the accused. This issue is not limited to threats only and in some cases, they have face actual violence which resulted in loss of life, property and loved ones. In some cases, witnesses are threatened and intimidated or even bribed for favorable statement or tampering with evidence. It is also noted with great concern that some witnesses are forcibly restrained to cooperate with investigating or prosecution authorities. Security challenges of a witness means asking a witness to testify in a certain way, to fabricate its statement, to conceal a material fact, to not report a crime or to not cooperate with police. (Hussain, 2015)

4.1 Famous Cases of Witness Intimidation in Pakistan

4.1.1 Wali Khan Babar Target Killing Case

Wali Khan Babar belonging from Balochistan, was a young news reporter of private news channel Geo News who was killed on 13th January 2011 by unknown assassins in Karachi. Later on, police have arrested some accused associated with the killing. During investigation and trial main witnesses of the case were threatened and forced to refrain from involvement in case. In two years, six witnesses including informants, police officials and members of investigation team connected with the case were killed. Lawyer of his case migrated from Pakistan and took asylum in US in mysterious conditions. Eliminating a witness becomes an easy method to obstruct justice when any journalist is killed (Witchel, E. n.d.)

4.1.2 Benazir Bhutto Assassination Case

Benazir Bhutto who was Pakistan's former Prime Minister was assassinated in a bomb blast and firing in Rawalpindi city on 27th December 2007 after attending an election campaign rally. Along with her several other political activists were also killed. The investigation and trial of this high-profile case was poorly handled and resultantly, it never met its true fate according to the demands of justice. There were several reasons of this tainted trial but one of the main reasons was witness intimidation.

Witnesses in their initial statements have clearly implicated Gen. Pervaiz Musharraf and two other senior police officials for not providing adequate security to Benazir Bhutto, but later on resiled from their statements by stating that security arrangements were satisfactory. In the circumstances, FIA failed to protect witnesses from the influence of the powerful and lost key witnesses in the process which makes it a clear case of witness intimidation (The Nation, 2015)

According to a news report, two witnesses received threatening phone calls apparently from Afghanistan. Witnesses claimed that they were threatened of serious consequences by a banned militant organization and later on the ATC court was also told by the witnesses and the prosecutor about the phone calls. Consequently, all five accused of this high-profile case were acquitted (Abbasi, 2013)

4.1.3 Sabeen Mehmood Murder Case

Sabeen Mehmood was a human rights activist who was running a social activities platform T2F at Karachi. On April 25 2015, when she was on her way back to home after attending a seminar on human rights violations in Balochistan at T2F when unknown assailants

opened fire upon her car near a busy area of defense in Karachi. Her mother was seriously wounded in the incident. Her driver rushed them to a nearby hospital but she succumbed to her injuries (Khan, 2017)

Key witness of case was Ghulam Abbas who was a police constable working as Sabkans driver. He was the only eyewitness in the case but unfortunately, he was killed in Karachi's Korangi area on September 7th 2015 (BBC, 2015)

4.1.4 Naqeebullah Mehsud Case

Naqeebullah Mehsud was a young aspiring model belonging from Waziristan tribal area but settled in Karachi. In January 2018 his bullet riddled body was found in the suburbs of Karachi. It was alleged that he was killed in a fake police encounter. This incident sparked anger nationwide and it was demanded that the matter be investigated and responsible be made answerable according to the law.

The incident was attributed to the then SSP Malir Rao Anwar, who was infamous for his role and involvement in the past encounters in Karachi. Rao Anwar, his 10 subordinate police officials and other 15 absconders were accused of the killing and stand trial. Two key witnesses of prosecution Rana Asif and Jahangir disowned their 161 statements and retracted from confession (Dawn, 2020). Later on, Rao Anwar and other accused facing trial were acquitted due to contradictory statements of prosecution witnesses.

4.1.5 Uzair Baloch Trial

Uzair Baloch is a local leader of Peoples Aman Committee based in Karachi's Liyari area who is alleged to be the leader of Liyari Gang War. He has been arrested on 30th January 2016 on the charges of violence, kidnapping, extortion, terrorism and murder of at least 198 people in various incidents.

According to a report of Pakistan Observer, the witnesses and prosecution officials of the Uzair Baloch trial were threatened. Report says that a key witness of the case was killed during the trial as a result of which Baloch was acquitted in at least 14 cases so far because the remaining witnesses are reluctant to come forward amidst threats. (Pakistan Observer n.d.)

4.1.5 Nazim Jokhio Case

Nazim Jokhio a local social worker, murder case was also a highlighted case in Sindh, Pakistan. Nazim Jokhio was killed after a severe torture and FIR was lodged against an

influential politician and a member of National Assembly of Pakistan, belonging from a major political party. After the registration of case the main accused flew to Dubai. However, the wife of the victim who was the witness of the case was pressurized and, in the circumstances, she recorded a video and announced that she is pardoning the accused and hence the accused were acquitted by court on the basis of out of court settlement (Wikipedia)

4. Other Issues of Witnesses in Pakistan's Criminal Justice System

As discussed in the preceding sections witnesses play an important role in criminal justice system. Due to the sensitive nature of their responsibility, they are vulnerable up to a great extent. They face various issues pertaining to their deposition in the court. They often depose against hardline criminals, terrorists, war-lords, professional murderers, psychopath killers, gang members, thieves, members of mobs, rapists and drug dealers etc. It is a matter of great concern that despite this difficult job no attention is paid on the issues they face as a consequence of their deposition. They have no protection and are exposed to a series of threats. They bear expenses and hardships of travelling to the courts. Not only this, they face a number of issues in court premises due to lack of facilities. After analyzing various reports, expert opinions, interviews and incidents, following core issues of witnesses has been enlisted as major issues.

4.1. Time, Costs and Expenses of Attending Court Proceeding

Witnesses travel from far and wide to assist the court in reaching a just conclusion of the case. They render a valuable service by spending their resources and time free of cost. It is another issue faced by witnesses to bear costs, expenses and time covered during travelling without being paid or compensated. There is no proper mechanism and arrangement for witnesses to be adequately compensated in reward of their hardships. (Friedman, Kontorovich, 2011). It is noted that courts do not consider or inquire this aspect of witnesses. In some cases, witnesses travel from far flung areas just to record their testimony. But unfortunately, courts do not give proper consideration of the issue. It also affects the deposition of the witnesses in the court up to great extent.

4.2. Adjournments

Our criminal justice system has many lacunas one of them is the problem of unnecessary and excessive adjournments of the proceedings. Adjournments casts a damaging impact on the trial because due to which a witness suffers a lot. (Asad, 2021). Section 19(8) of ATA deals with adjournments and states that there shall not be more than two adjournments, but this provision is not followed in stricto sensu. (ATA, 1997) Sections 229, 247, 344, 508 and 526 of CrPC deals with procedure adjournments in criminal trial but there is no time

limit for adjournments which makes the trial prone to several and unlimited adjournments. (CrPC, 1898). Sometimes the opposite parties seek unnecessary adjournments just to harass and exhaust the witness. (Munir, 2015). Due to this reason many important witnesses hesitate to cooperate and become reluctant to come forward and attend the court proceedings. Unnecessary adjournments irritate the witnesses and eventually they lose interest in the case. (Afzal, 2019).

4.3. Courtroom Environment

The environment of the courtroom has a great impact on the psychology and behavior of the witness. Those witnesses who are not familiar with the environment and who experience the environment for the first time, they become nervous by taking lot of mental pressure and lose confidence. Eventually they began to forget the important events and minor details of their deposition. In most of the cases this aspect is never considered by presiding officers of the court while recording such statements. Judges are duty bound to balance the scales of justice, as such they should note the behavior of witnesses and give them some time to refresh themselves. (Wilson, 2019)

Sometimes, the judges, the defense counsels and staff of court makes the situation worse by their strict behavior, resultantly, minor details slip from the mind of witness and the they suffer from sentence breakdown. Consequently, important facts remain unrecorded which is counted as a doubt, and according to legal principles benefit of such doubt is extended to the accused. In practice there is no mechanism for considering psychological pressure of courtroom environment. (Kerr & Bray, 1982)

Treatment given to a witness in courts had a lot of effect on his testimony. A witness should be treated with due respect and courtesy when he enters the court. In Pakistan it is generally practiced that witnesses are required to stand in witness box and remain standing during entire period of examination which will exhaust them for a long time. Comfort, dignity and convenience of the witnesses should be the concern of the court.

4.4. Confrontation with Accused

It is a natural behavior that a person never wants to confront his offender or culprit especially in the cases of murder, rape, sexual abuse, physical torture etc., in such cases confrontation of witness and victim with the accused in the courtroom subject them to suffer from mental trauma and shock. The situation become worse when the victim or witness is a child or woman. In such circumstances there are chances that the deposition of the witness becomes erroneous and defective.

4.5. Problem of Hostility of Witnesses

Although there is no statutory definition and clear mention of word hostility under our evidence law the Qanun e Shahadat Order 1984, but what is given under article 150 of the Order, is considered to be the basis of concept of hostile witness and whenever a witness under examination deposes contrary to his previous statement recorded u/s;161 crpc or contrary to the interests, version and case of the party calling him, it is said that the witness has turned hostile. Simply put, statement of a witness given before court of law, different and contradictory to his previous statement recorded before investigation agency. Such act of the witness is not only destructive to the cause of the party producing him but it also amounts to defeat the ends of justice. A witness turning hostile can be the cause of collapse of entire construction of the case, it wastes the precious time of the court and makes the mockery of entire criminal justice system by showing the path to criminals to walk free and escape justice.

Reasons for witness turning hostile are fear or intimidation. There are also some other factors such as bribery, monetary inducement and compromise of the witness with the accused. Witnesses retract from their statements because they know that there is no protection mechanism from in the whole process (Rawal, Aarti, 2023).

4.6. Easy Availability of Bail to Accused and its Impact on Witness

Another issue of witnesses is the mechanism and law of bail in Pakistan. Courts are normally inclined towards the protection of rights of the accused on the basis of innocence of accused. In this connection, courts do not hesitate to grant bail to the accused of heinous and non bailable offences even on minor grounds. It is also noted that it is a common practice in courts that while considering a bail application court do not give proper attention on the effects of bail on victim and its impact on vulnerable witnesses.

Whenever an accused of heinous offence gets bail promptly, the victims and witnesses feel unsafe while giving testimony, as a result of which it affects their statements which they depose under fear (Bajpai, 2009) Bail should not be granted in the cases of imprisonment for life or punishable with death where it appears that accused has committed the offence. Court should adopt the policy of judicial discretion while granting bail in such cases, the reason being that when an accused gets bail in heinous offences the witnesses feel unsafe and there will be high risks of witness intimidation and actual threat, particularly in the crimes of terrorism, murder, drug dealers and members of gang wars etc. (Zahoor, M.A. ,Bannian, 2022)

In a case the court has provided guidelines for granting of bail and has set out pre-requisites for acceptance of bail application such as background of accused, possibility of

misuse of bail, the impact of his release on witnesses and upon the society as well (1990 CriLJ 1531)

4.7. Circumstances Leading the Witness to Perjury

One of the main problems before our criminal justice system which is related to the witnesses is Perjury. Simple meaning and understanding of the perjury are the act of giving false evidence before court of law. However, deeper understanding of perjury is the act of witness to give false evidence before a court of law while he was sworn to tell the truth. Any statement given by a witness while he was under oath amounts to perjury. Moreover, another ingredient of perjury is the person giving that statement knows that the statement is not true and that it will mislead the court. Giving a false statement and committing perjury is also violation of oath.

Commission of perjury has always been a challenge before the courts however, despite the seriousness of the matter there is no legal or procedural tool or device which could be used to mitigate the chances of perjury. It seems that our criminal justice system has surrendered before this menace. There is complete silence from legal experts, jurists, legislators and researchers which could be used as a ray of hope in dealing with this problem in future, once and for all, which is a dangerous trend for our whole system of criminal justice mechanism (Zahoor & Anwar, 2020).

Convictions may be secured by legislation on the subject of perjury as initiated by some states and the crime of perjury itself is not difficult to prove as opposite to general perception. It can be proved simply by proving that the person gave two statements contradictory to each other and hence both statements cannot be true at the same time (Whitman, 1955).

A witness committing perjury loss its credibility and competency as a witness in future but also contaminates the whole case. As a result of which truthful witnesses are dealt with doubt and suspicion and face prolonged cross examination and harsh questions merely because the opposite counsels try hard to establish that this witness has committed perjury and cannot be trusted and, in that attempt, only one person suffers and that is a witness. According to McClintock “Hundreds of persons perjure themselves in the courts every day, except Sunday” (H.L. McClintock, 1940).

4.8. Problem of Accuracy and Fitness of Witness Memory

In general course of deposition before a court of law some witnesses face problem of remembering past facts, minor details, events of the incidents to which they are witness.

The accuracy of witness testimony plays an important role in criminal trial. However, situations may arise where witnesses face difficulty in deposing a fact before court of law, due to impact of some internal or external factors on witness memory. A witness has to remember all important and minute details of the incident during recording his statement. According to some surveys and experiments one factor that effects the memory of witness is age. Either too young age or too old age directly or indirectly effects the memory of witness leading to inaccuracy of testimony. Another factor which has impact on witness testimony is gender. There is a wide difference between the testimony and mental approach of male and female witnesses. Male witnesses often recall major events and can easily overcome emotional content, on the other hand, female witnesses pay attention on minute and important details which the male ignore or pay less attention, such as face structure, clothes, colors, jewelry or other wearing etc. but they cannot overcome emotional feelings during testimony as compared to male. (Ma, 2021).

Witness memory and its effect on testimony has long been subject of discussion among various scholars and researchers. It is founded that witness memory can be affected on various accounts. Scientific experiments and researchers show that witness memory cannot be fully relied and believed to be accurate, however, it cannot be negated as a form of evidence and still has its importance and significance in criminal and civil proceedings as well as arbitration proceedings (Kimberly. Wader, Cartwright-Finch, 2021).

There are various issues and aspects of discussion on the accuracy of witness testimony. The testimony of eyewitness although reliable but the aspect of emotionality attached with it cannot be denied and it is the emotionality which later on can be the subject of distortions. It is noted that the later recollection of the events can sometimes be very hard for even an eyewitness. Other factors which are counted to be the cause of witness memory accuracy include age, gender, personal characters, mood, behavior and emotional attachments etc (Tiwari, 2010).

Every crime and event leaves trace behind. Some traces are physical while some are mental. Physical traces are foot prints, fingerprints, blood-stained objects, crime weapons, injury marks, wounds, other materials found on crime spot while mental traces are memory of exact happening of an event. Courts, investigation authorities and forensic science rely on these traces as evidence. However, with the passage of time still eyewitness testimony is on high pedestal because of witness memory. Even now when an object is produced as evidence before court of law, there is still a requirement of a witness who could assist the court as to how, where, when and by whom such evidence was gathered and preserved as

per essential evidential protocols, hence it is proved that physical evidence has no credibility unless supported by a witness (Wills, 1995).

4.9. Prolonged and Unrestricted Cross-Examination

In adversarial system of trial process, cross examination is one of the most important opportunities given to the accused as a matter of right. It is devised to challenge all the statements given by the witness during his statement. It is aimed to provide an opportunity to the accused to defend himself in response to each and every allegation made against him by a witness. Accused and his counsel may use their entire efforts in rebuttal of the statements and to prove that whatever the witness has deposed is not true and trustworthy and hence not admissible in evidence against them. It is also a tool to establish dents and doubts in the prosecution version of the case (Doak, Jackson, Saunders, Wright, Gomez & Durdiyeva n.d.).

As per law, legal dictums and requirements of fair trial, cross-examination is the basic right of the accused. Law has armed the accused with the tool of cross-examination in order to check the veracity, truthfulness, credibility, admissibility and integrity of the statement. It is an important tool for the test and determination of truth and to help the innocent from being impeached and convicted in malicious cases. In our criminal justice system this tool is, however used, to harass, exhaust and restrict the witness from true and complete deposition and save the actual culprits from any conviction. In our judicial system this tool is misused without any restriction. There is no legal bar for the number questions put to the witness during cross-examination. On the other hand, our courts also do not restrict and allow practice of prolonged cross-examination (Roberts & Zuckerman, 2022). According to articles 146 and 148 judge has the power to restrict the counsel to drop or change the question but such power is rarely exercised (QSO,1948). Excessive questions which lead to violate the privacy of the witness are up to a large extent unconstitutional as article 14(1) of the constitution clearly states that dignity of man and privacy of his home are inviolable which clearly puts the privacy and dignity of a man on high footings.

The prolonged cross-examination leads the witness to exhaustion and confusion. Sometimes the counsels put too many irrelevant questions which serves no purpose for their case. The reason for such practice seems not to establish truth but to obtain a favorable answer out of witness's helplessness, confusion and exhaustion. Such practice is nevertheless against legal norms and contradictory to true intention of the legislature. (Margolis, 1974).

4.10. Lack of Facilities for Witnesses in Court Premises

Another issue faced by witnesses is lack of proper infrastructure and other basic facilities for witnesses in court premises. Majority of court buildings in Pakistani cities lacks basic facilities for litigating parties and witnesses. Facilities such as Shades, waiting rooms, proper seating, cleaning and drinking water, washrooms etc. are necessary for those witnesses who travel from far areas and wait for hours for their cases. Due to lack of facilities, they suffer a lot, which affects their performance during deposition.

4.11. Lack of Special Facilities for Special/Disable Witnesses in Court Premises

There are no special and reasonable adjustments in court buildings for special witnesses. Where people have a defective physical feature, it is highly difficult for them to court and depose of a fact within their knowledge. There are no parking areas, no wheelchairs, no wheelchair path and no sign language for disable witnesses in court buildings. It is one of the rights of the disable witness to use a third person known as “Intermediaries” who help the witness in police station and courts. The intermediaries will register themselves with courts and will assist the witness during examination, however, courts must ensure that the intermediaries do not change the meaning of the words and statements of the witness. Intermediaries are neutral persons approved by the court and they do not work for prosecution or defense (Nidirect Government Services).

5. Recommendations and Suggestions for Resolving Issues of Witnesses

- a) Proper facilities such as infrastructure facility, specified waiting area, drinking water and washrooms etc. and remuneration such as travel allowances, so that they may be encouraged to appear before court and cooperate with trial by recording their statements.
- b) Reforms in Pakistan Penal code to make it an offence to intimidate, induce, bribe, threaten, assault, and injury to him, his family and property. Currently there is no any penal section regarding any of the harm mentioned above to witnesses which makes them vulnerable.
- c) Full implementation of witness protection act and witness protection mechanism in all regions of Pakistan.
- d) Reforms in Criminal Procedure code to fix a limit for number of adjournments and to reduce unwarranted adjournments which creates inconvenience for witnesses and cause delay in trial. Courts must stop unnecessary adjournments and those lawyers who try to seek adjournments on flimsy grounds must be fined heavy costs and subordinate courts must prepare a list of those lawyers who repeatedly seek

adjournments. Lawyers holding license pledges to represent their clients and protect their interests but they fail to do so by seeking adjournments.

- e) Reforms in CRPC to amend the procedure of investigation and trial in the offences of rape and sexual violence particularly where the victim is a minor. Measures should be taken to record the statement of minor rape victim through modern technological devices and video links so that the minor may not suffer to confront the accused directly.
- f) Arrangements should be made to conduct the trial in-camera, so that the victim may not hesitate to describe the whole incident and record his statement in a free and comfortable atmosphere.
- g) Reforms should be made to reduce the chances of hostile witnesses and there should be a mechanism of inquiry into the reason of witness being hostile.
- h) Along with other measures of witness protection there should be an agreement between state (police and prosecution) and the witness to the extent that state will provide protection to the witness, his family and property and witness shall depose his true statement without fear or hesitation. Such protection should extend during entire course of trial and to all segments of witnesses without any discrimination.
- i) During the period of appearance before court, the witness should be treated with due respect, encouragement and be adequately compensated. The process of disbursement of compensation be made simple.
- j) Where people are reluctant to come forward as witnesses, necessary steps should be made to find out the actual reasons and causes behind their unwilling behavior.
- k) Judicial academies and other similar institutes should conduct training sessions for judges, lawyers, prosecutors and police about awareness and implementation of witness protection laws and witness protection mechanism.
- l) A witness should be fully assured that his life and interests be fully safeguarded before, after and during trial and such safety remains intact as long as there exists actual threat or intimidation.
- m) Witness protection must be reformed and rules applied according to the standards and procedure established by international court of criminal justice and international treaties to which Pakistan is a signatory.
- n) Wherever necessary psychological and emotional aid be provided to traumatized witnesses who suffered from a shock of extreme violence. Medical experts and

psychiatrists be provided to such witnesses. Currently there is no provision in our witness protection laws regarding psychological aid to witnesses.

- o) Witnesses should be directed by investigation authorities, lawyers and prosecutors, not to disclose and share the details of the case, their statement, any documentary evidence or any other information related to the case with anyone not authorized to have access to that information.
- p) Witnesses should be given awareness and made bound to serve, protect, preserve and safeguard the interests of the party on whose behalf he wishes to give testimony.
- q) Particular security devices should be installed at witness's residence such as CCTV, alarms, fencing where a witness face actual threats,
- r) Where a witness is a minor, or is a person with a physical impairment/disability a person known as a support person be allowed to remain by his side during his deposition,
- s) Court, prosecution and investigation authority must ensure that witness do not resile from its statement and in such cases, there should be proper mechanism to find out the actual reason of retraction or turning hostile,
- t) Judges should not sit as mute spectators when they clearly see that the defense counsels are harassing, annoying and speaking loud voices with witnesses in order to obtain an answer favorable to their version. Judges should realize the sensitivity of matter and ensure a proper limit of questions in cross-examination, protect the witness from ill treatment and upholding his dignity, honor and self-respect,
- u) In cases of sexual offences, restrictions should be imposed on improper cross-examination particularly when it relates to sexual history of the victim and where it amounts to violate the very privacy of the person as enshrined under our Constitution

6. Conclusion

Witnesses face a wide range of problems throughout world in general and in Pakistan in particular. Among these problems witness intimidation is on top. Due to witness intimidation and other problems the criminal justice system of Pakistan is under severe criticism for not resolving issues of witnesses. Many high-profile cases resulted in acquittal of accused due to critical situation of insecure environment for witnesses. Judiciary and executive are under an obligation to make sure that a witness gets a secure environment during recording of his statement with investigation authorities and before judicial proceeding because it is an essential element of free and fair trial. If these problems were

addressed on priority basis the status of Pakistan's rule of law might be better than the current situation.

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